

TEACHERS' STATE OF WELL-BEING AND RESILIENCE LEVEL: TOWARDS DESIGNING A WELLNESS PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the state of well-being and resilience of teachers at Ilagan East Integrated SPED Center as a basis for designing a wellness program. Specifically, it described the respondents' profile, assessed their well-being in terms of emotional, intellectual, physical, social, and spiritual health, determined their resilience in terms of family cohesion, personal competence and persistence, social skills and peer support, and spiritual influences, and tested the significant differences and relationships among these variables. A descriptive-survey research design was used, with total enumeration of 64 teachers with regular teaching loads during School Year 2024–2025. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution, weighted average mean, F-test, and Pearson's r-test. Findings revealed that the respondents were predominantly female, married, and middle-aged, with most earning ₱18,201–₱36,400 monthly and handling heavy workloads and multiple teaching assignments. Teachers manifested favorable emotional, intellectual, and social well-being, not quite favorable physical well-being, and very favorable spiritual well-being. In terms of resilience, the respondents demonstrated high levels in family cohesion, personal competence and persistence, social skills and peer support, and spiritual influences. Significant differences in selected dimensions of well-being and resilience were found when grouped according to civil status, monthly income, workload, and teaching assignments. Significant relationships were also identified between selected domains of well-being and resilience, particularly in emotional, physical, and spiritual health. The study concludes that while teachers generally demonstrate strong resilience, workload-related demands continue to affect their overall well-being. Hence, a responsive and evidence-based wellness program is

recommended to strengthen teacher support systems and promote holistic health and resilience.

Keywords: *teacher well-being, teacher resilience, wellness program, workload, public school teachers*

INTRODUCTION

The academic endeavor of every child begins at home, where parents serve as the first and most significant guides in the learning process. This influence extends into the school setting, where teachers become among the most important figures in children's formal education. Learners often show affection toward their teachers, follow their guidance, and imitate actions and behaviors that capture their interest. In this sense, teachers stand at the forefront of the learning process and play a vital role in shaping the character, attitudes, and development of the younger generation, as emphasized by Urhahne (2019) and Poling et al. (2022).

Being a teacher is both challenging and fulfilling. Molding young minds, listening to pupils' concerns, and touching their lives make teaching a noble profession. Children's learning often depends on how teachers help them understand lessons, and they also place value on the affection, encouragement, and support teachers provide. For this reason, teachers must remain good role models and sustain a healthy balance among their intellectual, emotional, and personal strengths. This idea is consistent with the view that social relationships and teacher well-being play an important role in teaching quality and student outcomes, as noted by Hascher and Waber (2021).

However, the demands of the profession often expose teachers to stress, exhaustion, and burnout, which may negatively affect their overall well-being. The growing complexity of educational environments, marked by heavy workloads, high expectations, and diverse student needs, underscores the need for focused interventions that support teachers' mental, emotional, and physical health. Research has shown that workload stress and long working hours are closely linked to reduced teacher well-being, highlighting the importance of institutional support and wellness-oriented programs for educators, as discussed by Hascher and Waber (2021) and Jerrim et al. (2021).

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has implemented several policies and initiatives to support the well-being of teachers. The "DepEd Required Health Standards" is an order to ensure the health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and personnel amid the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasizes mental health and psychosocial support services (MHPSS) for all stakeholders (Department of Education [DepEd], 2020).

Despite its critical importance, teachers' well-being remains an underexplored and undervalued area in many educational settings. Existing programs often focus on professional development or student support while overlooking the foundational role of teacher health and resilience. A comprehensive wellness program designed specifically

for educators has the potential to fill this gap by addressing their unique challenges and fostering holistic well-being.

The researcher, as one of the regular teaching staff in Ilagan East Integrated SPED Center, observed that teachers in their school are faithful in their teaching career. Enjoying what they are doing is simply the best attitude they have. But teachers are only human. They also tend to experience fatigue because of work overload and other aspects affecting them. Aside from the usual teaching routine, there were ancillary tasks given which led the teachers have a challenging career. Taking care of large number of children inside classroom premises and disciplining them needs effort to meet the demands of quality education. However, teachers do not want these young people to be affected by their burdens. They tend to fake a smile even they do not want; they laugh even they are in pain; they tend to be ok even they are not ok, and most of all they need to be strong because they are teachers. This experiential observation motivates the researcher to investigate the well-being and resilience of the teacher in her school premises to know whether teachers are still in good teaching shape.

Research Questions

The study aimed to probe into the state of well-being and resilience level of teachers as a basis for designing a wellness program.

It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. sex
 - b. age
 - c. civil status
 - d. monthly income
 - e. workload
 - f. number of teaching loads/assignment?
2. What is the state of well-being of teachers in terms of:
 - a. emotional health
 - b. intellectual health
 - c. physical health
 - d. social Health
 - e. spiritual Health
3. Is there a significant difference in the teacher's state of well-being when grouped according to their profile?
4. What is the resilience level of the respondents in terms of the following dimensions:
 - a. family cohesion
 - b. personal competencies and persistence
 - c. social skills and peer support
 - d. spiritual influences
 - e. Is there a significant difference in the teacher's level of resilience when grouped according to their profile?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the state of well-being of teachers and their level of resilience?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive survey method was applied in this study. According to Siedlecki (2020), survey research design is a systematic and structured approach to collect and analyze data from a sample population by administering the survey using questionnaires. The primary objective was to gather information on various topics, attitudes, opinions, or behaviors within a specific population. This design involved formulating a set of carefully crafted questions that are then distributed to a representative sample of individuals. Surveys conducted through various mediums, such as online platforms, telephone interviews, face-to-face interactions, or mailed questionnaires.

This design was used in this study to determine the profile, the state of well-being and resiliency level of the teachers.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Ilagan East Integrated SPED Center, located in Taft St, Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines. The research locale is a public elementary school that offers K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, SPED Curriculum for fast learners and learners with Special Educational Needs, Secondary Curriculum for Learners with Special Educational Needs, and Alternative Learning System.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 64 teachers with regular teaching loads at Ilagan East Integrated SPED Center for school year 2024- 2025. Total enumeration was used in this study. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by grade level and curriculum.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents

Teachers	F	%
ALS	1	1.56
SNED	12	18.75
Kindergarten	4	6.25
Grade 1	6	9.38
Grade 2	7	10.93
Grade 3	6	3.38
Grade 4	8	12.5

Grade 5	10	15.62
Grade 6	10	15.62
Total	64	100

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent and Assistant Schools Division Superintendent. After the approval, the researcher also sought permission from the School Principal of Ilagan East Integrated SPED Center. Since permission is granted, the researcher sought participation from the respondents of the study. The purpose of the study was to specify and inform them of the confidentiality of the data that they revealed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data gathered, the researchers employed different statistical treatments.

In analyzing the profile of the respondents, the frequency and percentage distributions were used.

In determining the well-being state and level of teacher's resilience, the weighted average mean (WAM) was applied.

The F-test determined the significant difference in well-being and resilience of teaching when group into profile.

Pearson's r-test was employed to reveal the significant relationship between the well-being and resilience of the teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Sex

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	14	21.88
Female	50	78.13
Total	64	100.00

Table 2 indicates the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their gender. The data shows that out of the total 64 teacher-respondents, 14 or **21.88%** are male and **78.13%** are female. This indicates that the teaching workforce in the institution under study is predominantly female. This demographic pattern reflects a broader trend commonly observed in the education sector, where females often outnumber males, particularly in basic education levels. The data reveals a significant gender imbalance in the respondent sample of teachers.

The overrepresentation of female teachers in the sample raises the possibility of gender-specific factors influencing the results. Men usually have career aspirations suitable to their capabilities rather than teaching profession. This gender disparity is often attributed to historical gender roles, societal expectations, and factors such as the flexibility teaching offers, which can be attractive to women rather than men.

b. Age

**Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age**

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-25	0	0.00
26-30	4	6.25
31-35	6	9.38
36-40	4	6.25
41-45	8	12.50
46-50	15	23.44
51-55	12	18.75
56-60	10	15.63
60 above	5	7.81
Total	64	100.00

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to age. The table reveals that majority of the respondents are middle-aged where 18.75 percent of the respondents are on the range of 51-55 years old; 15.63 percent are on the range of 56-60, and 12.50 percent are on the range of 41-45 years old. Middle age generally spans from 40–45 to 60–65 years of age according to the Lifespan Psychology by Laura Overstreet.

Research by Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2017), emphasizes that while older teachers may have developed resilience and professional coping strategies over time, they are also more likely to experience emotional exhaustion due to long-term exposure to high job demands. Similarly, Gu and Day (2013), found that veteran educators build emotional resilience through experience, but without adequate institutional support, this resilience may deteriorate, especially in demanding work environments. The predominance of older educators in the current data highlights the need for initiatives that go beyond surface-

level solutions and target deeper issues such as physical health management, stress reduction, and work-life balance.

Moreover, the absence of respondents in the 21–25 age group raises concerns about the sustainability of the teaching workforce and suggests potential issues in recruitment or early-career teacher retention. The few younger participants in the 26–35 range may benefit from mentorship and professional development opportunities that capitalize on the wisdom and resilience of their older colleagues. Acton and Glasgow (2015), argue that age-specific wellness programs are more effective because they address the distinct needs of each demographic segment. For older teachers, wellness interventions may include regular health screenings, ergonomic workplace adjustments, and retirement planning workshops. For younger educators, programs might focus on stress management, career development, and establishing a sense of belonging in the profession. Since most participants are at or approaching the late stages of their teaching careers, the educational sector should prioritize maintaining physical health, preventing burnout, and supporting emotional well-being. At the same time, the inclusion of structured peer support and mentorship can help bridge generational gaps, fostering a more resilient and connected professional community. In conclusion, the age distribution underscores the necessity for a comprehensive, age-responsive program that supports the holistic well-being of teachers and ensures resilience across all stages of their careers.

a. Civil Status

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	7	10.94
Married	55	85.94
Widow/Widower	2	3.13
Total	64	100.00

Table 4 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their civil status. The data above shows that most of the teacher-respondents are married, comprising 85.94% of the total sample. This is followed by single respondents with 10.94%, and a small proportion of widowed individuals, making up 3.13% of the sample. This demographic information is significant in understanding the respondents' context in relation to their well-being and resilience. Married individuals may face different stressors and support systems compared to single or widowed individuals. For instance, married teachers might benefit from family support, which can enhance emotional resilience, but they may also experience additional stress due to household and caregiving responsibilities.

The high percentage of married teachers suggests that most respondents likely have family responsibilities alongside their professional roles. This could affect their well-being both positively and negatively- marriage may offer emotional support and stability, which can help teachers cope with work-related stress may face additional pressures related to balancing work with family obligations, which could contribute to fatigue or burnout if not well-managed. Hence, single teachers may have more personal time and fewer family responsibilities, possibly allowing more flexibility and time for self-care. Widowed teachers may be experiencing emotional strain or loneliness.

b. Monthly Income

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Monthly Income

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 9,100	1	1.56
9,100-18,200	4	6.25
18,201-36,400	52	81.25
36,401-63,700	7	10.94
63,701-109,200	0	0.00
Total	64	100.00

Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to monthly income they receive. The table reveals that a significant majority or 81.25% earn between ₱18,201 and ₱36,400 per month. This range likely represents the standard salary bracket for public school teachers in the region, especially those with moderate years of service and no additional roles. A smaller portion or 10.94%, earn within the ₱36,401 to ₱63,700 bracket, possibly reflecting those with higher ranks with additional responsibilities, or longer years of service. Meanwhile, four respondents fall under the ₱9,100 to ₱18,200 income range, which may indicate entry-level positions or part-time employment. Only one respondent earns below ₱9,100, suggesting limited financial resources that could negatively affect well-being. Notably, no respondents reported a monthly income above ₱63,700.

Income is a powerful determinant of well-being and resilience, particularly in helping individuals manage stress, access healthcare, and maintain a work-life balance. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2013), income security significantly affects an individual's capacity to meet basic needs, cope with adversity, and maintain mental health. In the context of teaching, limited financial resources may contribute to chronic stress, especially when coupled with high job demands and personal responsibilities. Day and Qing (2009) assert that financial strain among teachers can erode job satisfaction and contribute to emotional fatigue, ultimately impacting performance and morale. Teachers earning on the lower end of the income scale may struggle to afford wellness-related expenses, such as mental health counseling, gym

memberships, nutritious food, or even rest and recovery activities, all of which are vital to sustaining professional resilience.

According to McLellan and Steward (2015), financial security fosters autonomy and control, which are critical components of resilience in high-stress professions like teaching. When educators are constantly burdened by economic insecurity, their ability to bounce back from challenges, innovate in their teaching, or engage in professional growth may be compromised. The data's implication that most teachers fall within a mid-range income bracket suggests a potential vulnerability to financial stressors, especially in times of inflation or unexpected expenses, unless supplemented by supportive policies and benefits.

Additionally, policies that advocate for salary upgrades, incentives, and financial literacy training can enhance not only economic well-being but also long-term resilience. Acton and Glasgow (2015), support the idea that workplace wellness is not solely about physical health but is deeply tied to economic and psychological stability.

In conclusion, the monthly income distribution of the respondents reflects a teaching workforce that is financially constrained, with limited upward mobility within their current roles.

c. Workload (No. of hours in Teaching)

**Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to
Workload or Number of Hours in Teaching**

Workload	Frequency	Percentage
0-3 hours	0	0.00
4-6 hours	27	42.19
7-10 hours	37	57.81
Total	64	100.00

Table 6 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to the number of hours in teaching. The data shows that all respondents teach more than 3 hours a day where majority or 57.81 percent work for 7-10 hours. In an interview with the teachers in IESCS, they disclosed that they are having difficulties in having excess workload. Aside from the burden in paper works, they do not have much time to be with their families. They also added that at times, their family do not understand why they need to work more than the working hours.

According to Kyriacou (2001), teaching is inherently stressful due to its emotionally demanding nature, and this stress is exacerbated when teachers are required to work long hours without adequate rest or support. The high percentage of respondents working 7–10 hours daily raise concerns about the risk of chronic stress and emotional exhaustion, especially when teaching hours are extended by non-instructional tasks such as grading, lesson planning, and administrative reporting. This can erode teachers'

personal time, limit opportunities for self-care, and negatively impact their resilience—defined as the ability to recover from professional challenges and maintain motivation over time.

Furthermore, studies by Day and Gu (2010), emphasize that teacher resilience is not solely an internal trait but is heavily shaped by external working conditions, such as workload, collegial support, and institutional policies. The data in this study suggests that without intervention, prolonged teaching hours may compromise teachers' ability to sustain passion and commitment to their profession. Teachers working long hours are also more likely to suffer from sleep deprivation, reduced time with family, and poorer physical health outcomes—factors that collectively diminish well-being. The Philippine Department of Education has acknowledged these challenges in recent years, encouraging workload reviews and mental health initiatives, yet implementation often lags at the local level.

The data clearly indicates that most teachers in the study carry a heavy daily workload, which can be a significant source of stress and a barrier to well-being and resilience. To design an effective wellness program, this workload must be addressed both through policy-level changes and through personal coping and support mechanisms. Ensuring that teachers are not overburdened is not just a matter of well-being—it is essential for sustaining an effective, motivated, and resilient teaching workforce. Considering this, the wellness program proposed in this study should specifically address workload management and recovery strategies. This includes time-management training, advocacy for more balanced class assignments, policies that limit excessive teaching loads, and institutional support such as hiring additional staff or providing protected time for lesson preparation and rest. Resilience-building components should also include stress-reduction techniques such as mindfulness, physical wellness activities, and peer counseling systems. As supported by the work of Beltma et al. (2011), resilience programs are most effective when they acknowledge the structural realities teachers face—chief among them being workload—and aim to reduce or mitigate these stressors directly.

d. Teaching Assignment

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According Teaching Assignment

Teaching Assignment	Frequency	Percentage
0-3 subjects	16	25.00
4-6 subjects	23	35.94
7-10 subjects	25	39.06
Total	64	100.00

The data reveals the distribution of teaching assignments based on the number of subjects handled by the respondents. A substantial proportion of the teachers are

handling 7 to 10 subjects, indicating a high workload. This is followed by 35.94% teaching 4 to 6 subjects, and 16 respondents with 0 to 3 subjects, suggesting relatively lighter teaching loads. The findings indicate that most of the respondents have 7-10 subjects per day. This kind of workloads greatly affect their time management, making lesson plans, activities, instructional materials to different subjects and constant pressure to meet deadlines that will lead to many responsibilities, teachers have less time for lesson preparation, student feedback, and instructional improvement.

Handling multiple subjects often involves extensive lesson planning, preparation, grading, and additional responsibilities, all of which contribute to stress and potential burnout. Such workload-related pressures may lower job satisfaction, reduce work-life balance, and negatively impact emotional and physical health over time.

A study of da Silva et al., (2024), backed up these findings which examined the relationship between teachers' workload and their quality of life. It found that teachers with heavy workloads reported lower quality of life, particularly in physical and mental health domains. This suggests that the demands of teaching assignments can have significant implications for teachers' overall well-being.

2. What is the state of well-being of teachers in terms of:

a. Emotional Health

**Table 8
State of Well-being of Teachers in Terms of Emotional Health**

Emotional Health		Mean	Qualitative Description	State of Emotional Health
1	Maintaining positive and energetic attitude inside the classroom affect my wellbeing	3.10	Agree	Favorable
2	I feel happy about my work.	3.63	Strongly Agree	Very Favorable
3	I feel irritated dealing with pupils' misunderstanding.	2.3	Disagree	Favorable
4	There is difficulty in regaining my calm after setting some conflicts.	2.45	Disagree	Favorable
5	Negligence and inattention of pupils affect my tolerance.	2.13	Disagree	Favorable
6	Individual differences of pupils sometimes make me angry.	2.46	Disagree	Favorable
7	Adjusting to new teaching practices makes me feel stressed.	2.30	Disagree	Favorable

8	Keeping the safety protocols inside the classroom sometimes make me feel having no control.	2.10	Disagree	Favorable
9	I feel distracted when working too long on devices.	2.54	Agree	Not quite favorable
10	There is a feeling of frustration about career progressions.	2.54	Agree	Not quite favorable
11	I feel bothered by little interest or pleasure in doing things.	2.41	Disagree	Favorable
12	I feel bothered by feeling down, depressed or hopeless.	2.45	Disagree	Favorable
13	I feel bothered by feeling bad about myself - or that I'm a failure or have let myself or my family down.	2.42	Disagree	Favorable
14	I feel bothered by thoughts that I would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way.	2.15	Disagree	Favorable
15	I have a hard time coping with the daily demands in school and at home.	2.46	Disagree	Favorable
	Total Mean	2.49	Disagree	Favorable

The state of well-being of teachers in terms of emotional health is presented in Table 8. The data shows that the teachers generally Disagree with the statements which indicates a favorable emotional health. The data reveals that the negative indicators do not affect the teachers' performance inside the classroom. It further presents that they are happy with their work. The result also shows that the teachers can maintain their emotions in work and are not irritated with pupils' misunderstanding. They also have no difficulty in regaining their calmness after setting some conflicts. In addition, negligence and inattention of pupils do not affect teachers' tolerance. Moreover, individual differences also do not make them angry garnering a mean of 2.46. and adjustment to new teaching practices do not make them stressed. They also have control in keeping the safety protocols inside the classroom and they are not bothered by little interest, feeling down, depressed nor hopelessness, feeling bad about themselves, nor thoughts of hurting themselves. Furthermore, teachers do not have hard time coping with the daily demands in school. These results suggest a favorable emotional state.

Teachers' well-being is affected by positive and energetic attitude inside the classroom. They also claim that they feel distracted when working too long on devices and frustrated about career progressions. These results suggest a not quite favorable state. The pervasive use of devices in classrooms, while intended to aid instruction, often leads to distractions. Teachers struggle to keep students focused as devices enable off-task behavior, which reduces student engagement and overall classroom productivity.

This creates frustration for teachers who feel unable to effectively manage their classrooms and deliver instruction as intended. Teachers' distraction from prolonged device uses stems from the challenge of managing student engagement in a tech-saturated environment, which increases stress and burnout.

Lack of support from school leadership, increasing workloads, and higher expectations without adequate resources contribute significantly to job dissatisfaction and career frustration. Often, the high requirements in career progression are also a threat. Since most of the respondents are in middle age, the high expectations and continuous technological advancement demands will affect their eagerness to push through assessments and promotions. Abele et al. (2012), explains that there was a problem in maintaining health being among teachers in career progression since employment and career development are important goals in most teachers' life. Teachers must pursue a high position to earn their living, can afford to spend for activities to maintain healthy despite new strategies and approach in teachings.

b. Intellectual Health

Table 9
State of Well-being of Teachers in Terms of Intellectual Health

Intellectual Health		Mean	Qualitative Description	State of Intellectual Health
1	I am confident to think or express my own ideas and opinions.	3.23	Agree	Favorable
2	I know that I had something important to contribute to society.	3.38	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
3	I had trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television.	2.27	Disagree	Favorable
4	I tend to take a long time to get over setbacks in my life.	2.31	Disagree	Favorable
5	It is hard for me to snap back when something bad	2.26	Disagree	Favorable
Total Mean		2.708	Agree	Favorable

Table 9 exhibits the factors affecting the intellectual well-being of teachers with an overall mean of 2.708. The data reveals that teachers can concentrate easily on things such as reading or watching and they do not take a long time to get over setbacks in their life. Furthermore, they easily snap back when something bad happens. They also are confident to think or express their own ideas and opinion. These results suggest favorable state of intellectual health. The findings imply that teachers are intellectually resilient. They are confident all the time specially in expressing their thoughts and a deep

understanding of their subject matter, which empowers them to articulate ideas clearly and respond to challenges effectively. Regular participation in professional development and training further enhances their pedagogical skills and adaptability to new teaching methods, boosting their assurance in professional interactions.

Moreover, they know that they have something important to contribute to the society as teachers suggesting very favorable result. With this result, teachers see themselves as role models and agents of positive change, which reinforces their belief that their contributions matter not only to their students but to the community at large. This deep connection to their meaningful work and the recognition of their influence on future generations fosters the confidence needed to express their thoughts openly and advocate for educational and social improvements. The data indicates that teachers generally maintain a favorable level of intellectual health, characterized by confidence, purpose, and cognitive stability. While some indicators hint at areas for potential development—such as managing concentration and recovering from setbacks—these do not significantly detract from the overall positive outlook. These insights are vital for informing wellness program components that aim to support intellectual stimulation, critical thinking, and mental clarity, all of which are essential for maintaining teacher effectiveness and resilience in the profession. Intellectual well-being in teachers is characterized by meaningful engagement, autonomy in professional learning, and cognitive vitality. It plays a critical role in sustaining teachers' motivation, job satisfaction, and effectiveness in the classroom, while its erosion can contribute to stress and professional dissatisfaction.

These findings align with the literature emphasizing that intellectual health is not limited to academic performance or IQ, but includes a person's ability to think critically, engage meaningfully, and recover cognitively from stress. According to Hettler's (1976) Six Dimensions of Wellness Model, intellectual wellness involves engaging in creative and stimulating mental activities, expanding knowledge, and maintaining a sense of purpose—all of which appear present among the respondents. Moreover, the positive self-perceptions shown in the results are reflective of teachers' resilience and adaptability, key qualities highlighted in studies by Gu & Day (2013), who stress the importance of identity and agency in sustaining well-being among educators.

c. Physical Well-being

Table 10
State of Physical well-being of teachers in terms of Physical Health

Physical Well- Being		Mean	Qualitative Description	State of Physical Health
1	Misbehavior of pupils caused me restlessness that I cannot manage such misconduct easily.	2.35	Disagree	Favorable

2	I feel confused when dealing with multiple tasks and responsibilities.	2.66	Agree	Not quite favorable
3	I had trouble falling sleep, staying asleep, or sleeping too much.	2.54	Agree	Not quite favorable
4	I often experienced feeling tired or having little energy.	2.74	Agree	Not quite favorable
5	I often experienced having poor appetite or overeating.	2.53	Agree	Not quite favorable
6	I often experienced moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed.	2.41	Disagree	Favorable
7	I often cannot breathe comfortably.	2.41	Disagree	Favorable
	Total Mean	2.52	Agree	Not quite favorable

Table 10 shows the state of physical well-being of teachers. As can be seen, the teachers agree that they: a) feel confused when dealing with multiple tasks and responsibilities, b) had trouble falling sleep, staying asleep, or sleeping too much; often experienced feeling tired or having little energy and c) often experienced having poor appetite or overeating. These suggest that they are not physically well.

On the contrary, they disagree that misbehavior of pupils caused them restlessness that they cannot manage such misconduct easily, that they often experienced moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed and they often cannot breathe comfortably. The data does not show alarming health issues; it reflects a trend toward physical exhaustion and stress among teachers. This highlights the need for wellness interventions that focus on rest, sleep hygiene, balanced nutrition, and stress management to support teachers' physical health and prevent long-term burnout.

This is proven by Madigan et al. (2013) during their systematic review of the linkage of burnout and physical wellbeing of teachers. The findings support the notion that teachers who experience burnout may be at risk for worse physical health. Madigan et al.'s review validates that burnout often caused by overwork, including digital workload not only impacts attention and focus but also has physical consequences, supporting the explanation about why teachers feel distracted and overwhelmed.

d. Social Well-being

Table 11
State of Well-being of Teachers in Terms of Social Health

Social Well-being		Mean	Qualitative Description	State of Social Well-being
1	I have a good relationship with my students.	3.48	Strongly Agree	Very Favorable
2	I have a good relationship with the parents of my students.	3.42	Strongly Agree	Very Favorable
3	My relationship with co-teachers matters to me.	3.49	Strongly Agree	Very Favorable
4	I feel upset about taking some classes when my fellow co-teacher is not around.	2.28	Disagree	Favorable
5	My social health affects my professional efficacy.	2.49	Disagree	Favorable
6	My workload has taken much of my time for my family.	2.69	Agree	Not quite favorable
7	I tend to sacrifice recreational activities with my family due to work.	2.88	Agree	Not quite favorable
Total Mean		2.96	Agree	Favorable

Table 11 shows the state of well-being of teachers in terms of social health. Findings show that teachers have good relationship among the students, parents, and even co-workers with an overall mean of 2.96 and a favorable analysis. Teachers have good relationship with their students and parents. They also think that their relationship with their co-teachers matters to them. Moreover, teachers do not feel upset about taking some classes when a co-teacher is not around nor agree that their social health affects their professional efficacy. These statement implies a favorable relation with peers. The respondents believe that a healthy environment and communication with the people around them can create a healthy social environment.

However, teachers claim that their workload has taken much of their time for their family, and they tend to sacrifice their recreational activities with their family due to workloads. This suggests that respondents feel a more significant impact on their ability

to engage in recreational activities with their family due to their workload. Respondents acknowledge that their professional commitments leave them with limited time for family activities, which could contribute to feelings of stress or dissatisfaction in their family relationships. These suggest not quite favorable state.

The result is backed up by the study of Deshmukh and Deshmukh (2018) that women with higher workloads reported significant difficulty in balancing work with family responsibilities. Many respondents indicated that their workload consumed much of their time, leaving them with little or no time for family activities.

e. Spiritual Well-being

Table 12
State of Well-being of Teachers in Terms of Spiritual Health

Spiritual Well-being		Mean	Qualitative Description	Sate of Spiritual well-being
1	I have inner peace.	3.58	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
2	I believe that God loves me and cares about me especially when I work with happiness.	3.84	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
3	I feel that life is a positive experience.	3.68	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
4	I believe in the goodness of all people-my learners and colleagues.	3.71	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
5	I love myself and at peace with my work.	3.76	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
6	I feel very fulfilled and satisfied with life.	3.59	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
7	I feel a sense of well-being about the direction my life is headed in.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
8	My faith helps me to make decisions.	3.78	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
9	Most people are friendly to me.	3.59	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
10	My relationship to God helps me not to feel lonely at work.	3.87	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
11	I have good moral and decent beliefs.	3.8	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
12	I feel most fulfilled and reflect about the meaning and purpose of life.	3.8	Strongly Agree	Very favorable

13	My relationship with God contributes to my sense of well-being.	3.99	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
14	I believe that God is concerned about my problems.	3.91	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
15	I believe there is some real purpose for my life in teaching.	3.87	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
16	I make efforts to deal with difficult problems of humanity by religious means.	3.68	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
17	I maintain positive feelings, hope and satisfaction.	3.8	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
18	I believe in God more than entertaining sadness, anxiety and anger.	3.87	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
19	I help without expecting in return.	3.78	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
20	I take time to think about what's important in life.	3.82	Strongly Agree	Very favorable
	Total Mean	3.768	Strongly Agree	Very favorable

Table 12 exhibits the state of well-being of teachers in terms of spiritual health. Data shows that teachers have a good commitment to God with an overall mean of 3.768 and a very favorable analysis. Teachers believed that they have inner peace and they also believed that God loves and cares for them especially when they work with happiness. They felt that life is a positive experience and believe in the goodness of all people (learners and colleagues). They strongly agree that they love themselves and their peace at work and they feel fulfilled and satisfied with life and feel a sense of well-being about the direction in their life is heading. They claim that their faith helps them to make decisions and their relations with God helps them not to feel lonely at work, and they feel most fulfilled and reflect about the meaning and purpose of life. Teachers strongly agree that their relationship with God contribute to their sense of well-being and believed that God is concerned about their problems. They also believe that there is some real purpose for their life in teaching. Lastly, they take time to think about what is important in life. Teachers' strong agreement to all the indicators suggest a very favorable spiritual well-being.

The data reveals that teachers find strength, comfort, and guidance in their faith and relationship with God, particularly in navigating their personal and professional challenges. They report a strong sense of inner peace, purpose, and fulfillment, especially in their teaching vocation. Furthermore, teachers demonstrate a positive outlook on life, value moral integrity, and maintain hope and compassion in their daily interactions. Their

belief in the goodness of others, commitment to self-reflection, and practice of altruism further reinforce a spiritually healthy mindset. Overall, the findings reflect a group of educators who are not only spiritually grounded but also emotionally resilient, morally guided, and purpose-driven in their profession.

The results also shows that teachers believe in God and the goodness of people, which then leads to positive feeling and spiritual well-being. Teachers also show significant fulfillment in life and professional work because of their faith and good morality. The study of Heidari et al. (2022) supports the findings that spiritual health had positive and significant relationship with teachers' organizational commitment and positive outlook in life.

3. Is there a significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being when grouped according to their profile?
a. Emotional Health

Table 13
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher's Emotional Health
When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Emotional Health and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.1570	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.1139	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0288	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Monthly Income	0.0397	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Workload	0.0500	P=0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.0290	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 13 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the teachers' emotional health when grouped according to their profile. The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 except for sex and age. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the teachers' emotional state when grouped according to civil status, monthly income, workload, and number of teaching loads. The data shows that teachers who are married, with monthly income of ₱36,401 - 63,700, with 4-6 working hours, and with 7-10 teaching assignments have better emotional state compared to the rest of the groups. Teachers with heavier workloads or multiple teaching assignments face compounded stress from administrative tasks, classroom management, and preparation time, which can erode emotional resilience and contribute to burnout.

However, there is no significant difference in the teachers' emotional health when grouped according to their sex and age. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05

significance level meaning the teachers have similar emotional health regardless of their sex and ages. These findings collectively emphasize that emotional health in teaching is shaped less by intrinsic traits like age or sex because no matter what age or gender, teachers must do their job, the same responsibilities-that is to teach the learners.

These results suggest that personal circumstances like civil status and financial stability, as well as job-related factors such as workload and teaching responsibilities, play a substantial role in shaping the emotional well-being of educators. Therefore, it is essential for educational institutions to consider these variables when designing support systems and interventions aimed at promoting teacher wellness. The study of Ozamiz-Etxebarria et al. (2021) found out that having family creates a greater impact on the feelings of stress. Having to deal with a heavy workload, combined with the stress of carrying out family care duties, may be one of the reasons why teachers with children have suffered from higher levels of stress.

b. Intellectual Health

Table 14
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher’s Intellectual Health
When Grouped according to their Profile

Teacher’s Intellectual Health and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.1291	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.2181	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0842	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Monthly Income	0.2336	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Workload	0.0174	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.0901	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the teachers’ state of well-being in terms of intellectual health when grouped according to their profile is presented in Table 14. It is evident from the results that the F-probability values are greater than 0.05 except for workloads. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the teachers’ state of well-being in terms of intellectual health when grouped according to their sex, age, civil status, monthly income, and number of teaching loads. It implies that the teachers have similar state of intellectual health regardless of their sex, age, civil status, monthly income, and number of teaching loads.

On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the teachers' intellectual health when grouped according to their workloads. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 significance.

The study shows that the teachers with 4-6 workloads have a better state of intellectual health. The findings of this study negate the findings of Magalong and Torreon (2021) which states that there is no significant difference between the workload of teachers and their intellectual health. The authors concluded that teaching effectiveness does not depend on the tasks and functions given to the teachers, hence, they are still achieving satisfactory rating despite the fact that they are bombarded with designation and responsibility.

c. Physical Health

Table 15
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher's Physical Health
When Grouped according to their Profile

Teacher's Physical Health and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.0221	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Age	0.1792	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.1618	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Monthly Income	0.0328	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Workload	0.0048	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.1618	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 15 displays the results of the test of significant difference in the teachers' state of physical health when grouped according to their profile. The results reveal that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 for sex, monthly income, and workload. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is significant difference in the teachers' state of physical health when grouped according to their sex, monthly income, and workload. It further reveals that teachers who are female, with monthly income of ₱18,201 – 36,400, and with 4-6 workloads have better physical health state of well-being than the rest of the groups. The findings suggest that sex and monthly income are significantly associated with teacher physical health, while age and the number of teaching loads are not. The strongest association is between workload and physical health, indicating that heavier workloads negatively affect teachers' well-being.

The study of Jomuad et al. (2021) found similar results indicating workload has a significant impact on the level of burnout experienced and influences their performance.

The study recommended that every school administrator should adhere to proper workload assignment. According to some teachers that I interviewed, monthly income is also significant in their physical health because if they cannot afford to spend money on some recreational activities and enjoy rest activities because of their small salary, it does affect their body. However, there is no significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of physical health when grouped according to their age, civil status, and number of teaching loads. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. It implies that teachers have similar state of well being in terms of physical health regardless of their age, civil status, and number of teaching loads.

d. Social Health

Table 16
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher's Social Health When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Social Health and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.1401	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Age	0.1694	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.1026	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Monthly Income	0.0362	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Workload	0.0048	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.1026	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of social health is displayed in Table 16. It is evident from the results that F-probability values are less than 0.05 for monthly income and workload. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of social health when grouped according to their monthly income and workload. Results of the study show that the teachers with monthly income of ₱9,100 – 18,200 and with 4-6 workloads have better state of social health than the rest of the groups of teachers.

These findings highlight the need for school administrators and policymakers to consider economic and workload-related factors when designing class programs for teachers. Ensuring manageable workloads and providing adequate compensation may contribute positively to their overall social health and professional satisfaction as they are concentrated in teaching when they don't have problems financially. Financial stability makes them at peace mentally and emotionally. Manageable workloads can also make the respondents apply their time management skills in teaching and doing extra activities in the school, family and community.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of social health when grouped according to their sex, age, civil status, and number of teaching loads. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level. It further means that the teachers have similar state of social health regardless of their sex, age, civil status, and number of teaching loads. Zubair et al., (2020) in their study found a negative correlation between high workload and social health. Workers who reported heavier workloads tended to experience greater work-related stress, which in turn negatively affected their social relationships. The study emphasized that individuals with high work demands often have less time and energy to invest in social interactions, leading to feelings of social isolation and reduced quality of social connections.

e. Spiritual Health

Table 17
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher's Spiritual Health
When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Spiritual Health and the following Profile	P-value of F		Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.2153		$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.2150		$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0266		$P < 0.05$	Reject Ho	Significant
Monthly Income	0.0724		$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Workload	0.0076		$P < 0.05$	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.1809		$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 17 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of spiritual health when grouped according to their profile. The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 for civil status and workloads. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of spiritual health when grouped according to their civil status and workload. Data shows that the teachers who are widows and with 7-10 workloads have better spiritual health state of well-being.

However, there is no significant difference in the teachers' state of well-being in terms of spiritual when grouped according to their age, sex, monthly income, and number of teaching loads. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level. It implies that the teachers have no difference in their spiritual health state of well-being when classified by the aforementioned profile variables. The results indicate further that

the teachers have similarities in their spiritual health state of well-being regardless in their sex, age, monthly income, and number of teaching loads.

The findings suggest that spiritual health among teachers is more closely related to their personal relationships and professional demands compared to their demographic characteristics or income level. Particularly, a heavier workload may hinder opportunities for spiritual engagement, while a teacher’s civil status might influence their access to emotional and spiritual support. These insights underscore the importance of holistic teacher programs that not only consider workload management but also foster spiritual and emotional support systems that reflect teachers’ varied life circumstances. Garg et al., (2019) found that high work stress resulting from increased workload led to reduced spiritual well-being. Employees who faced greater job demands, including long hours and heavy responsibilities, reported feeling more disconnected from their spiritual practices. These individuals often lacked the time and mental energy needed for activities that nurtured their spiritual health, such as meditation, prayer, or participating in spiritual communities.

The study of Lopez et al., (2017) also found out that married individuals or those with familial support systems tended to have stronger spiritual lives. Having a partner or family provided them with the emotional and social support necessary to foster spiritual growth. Additionally, being in a committed relationship often led individuals to engage in spiritual practices as a form of mutual support or shared values, which contributed to a stronger sense of spiritual community.

4. What is the level of resilience of the respondents in terms of the following dimensions:

a. Family cohesion

**Table 18
Resilience of Teachers in Terms of Family Cohesion**

Family Cohesion	Mean	Analysis of Interpretation
1. I have similar understanding with my family on what is essential in life.	3.58	High
2. I feel thrilled with family.	3.55	High
3. My family is characterized by healthy coherence	3.57	High
4. Under challenging periods, my family keeps a positive outlook on the future	3.8	High
5. Facing other people, my family acts loyal towards one another.	3.71	High
6. In our family, we like to do things together	3.65	High
7. When needed, someone in our workplace can help me.	3.6	High
Total Mean	3.637	High

The teachers' resilience in terms of Family Cohesion is shown in table 18. The result shows that teachers are cohesive with their family with an overall mean 3.637. The study shows that teachers have similar understanding with their family on what is essential in life with a mean of 3.58. They also feel thrilled with their family with a mean of 3.55. Their families are characterized by healthy coherence with a mean of 3.57. Under challenging periods, teachers' families keep a positive outlook on the future with a mean of 3.8. Their family acts loyal towards one another when facing other people with a mean of 3.71. They do things together and when needed, they help each other with means of 3.65 and 3.60, respectively. These results show high resilience of teachers in terms of family cohesion.

It can be surmised that factors such as having similar understanding with their family, having a positive outlook in life, and working together contributed in the positive result. The consistently high ratings across all items suggest that family cohesion is a strong pillar of resilience for teachers. Teachers benefit emotionally and psychologically from having families that share common values, maintain strong emotional bonds, show loyalty, and support each other, especially during times of stress. The high score on optimism during challenges (M = 3.80) particularly underscores how positive family dynamics help buffer the impact of adversity, which is a core component of resilience. Moreover, the inclusion of workplace support (Item 7) in the domain of family cohesion reflects an expanded view of resilience—one that incorporates supportive relationships both at home and in the professional environment.

The findings affirm that teachers with cohesive family relationships are more likely to exhibit resilience, highlighting the importance of nurturing both family and professional support systems in sustaining teachers' well-being and ability to cope with stressors in their work and personal lives. Teachers can do everything, can survive and more productive with the support of family and their loved ones. It is in this data that despite problems inside or outside the job place, a family, colleagues and friends can make life's problem easier.

The result is similar to the study of Hui and Abdullah (2020) which found that family cohesion has the highest mean among the factors of teachers' resilience, thus, teachers have their family who listens, love, and supports them.

b. Personal Competence and Persistence

**Table 19
Resilience of Teachers in Terms of Personal Competence and Persistence**

Personal Competence and Persistence	Mean	Analysis of Interpretation
1. I can adapt to change.	3.7	High
2. Under pressure, I can focus and think clearly	3.47	High
3. I prefer to take the lead in problem-solving	3.42	High
4. I cannot easily discourage by failure	3.31	Low
5. I think of someone as a strong person	3.54	High

6. If necessary, I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people	3.14	Low
7. I can handle unpleasant feelings, such as anger or fear	3.34	Low
8. I like challenges	3.22	Low
9. I can work hard to attain my goals	3.63	High
Total Mean	3.42	High

Table 19 shows the resilience of teachers in terms of Personal Competence and Persistence with an overall mean of 3.42. The result presents that teachers may sometimes find it difficult to recover from failure and unpleasant feelings, however, they still attain goals and stand strong.

Teachers can adapt to change and can focus and think clearly under pressure. Teachers also are highly resilient in taking the lead in problem-solving and think of them as strong person, and in working hard. The findings suggest that teachers demonstrate considerable resilience in several key areas of personal competence. They can adapt to change, maintaining focus under pressure, and working persistently toward goals. These traits are critical for navigating the daily challenges and demands of the teaching profession.

However, the results also reveal vulnerabilities in certain aspects of persistence and emotional resilience. Lower ratings on discouragement by failure, emotional regulation, and willingness to face difficult situations like making unpopular decisions or embracing challenges that indicate some teachers may struggle with internal stress responses and decision-making in high-pressure contexts. These areas represent potential growth points where support and training could enhance teachers' full capacity for resilience. Overall, the respondent teachers have high level of resilience in terms of personal competence.

Ross and Scanes (2025) noted that the persistence of intrinsic motivation of teaching focused academics despite the frustration of lack of control, is like studies which also found in the Self Determination Theory that explains defines intrinsic and several types of extrinsic motivation and outlines how these motivations influence situational responses in different domains of support.

c. Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 20
Resilience of Teachers in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support

Peer Support	Mean	Analysis of Interpretation
1. In my workplace, I enjoy being together with other people	3.65	High

2. New friendships are something I make quickly in the workplace	3.57	High
3. Meeting new people in my workplace is something I am good at	3.49	High
4. In my workplace, when I am with others, I easily laugh	3.54	High
5. I can discuss personal issues with other peers	3.59	High
6. The bonds between my peers and I are strong	3.46	High
7. I get support from my peers	3.49	High
Total Mean	3.54	High

The resilience level of teachers in terms of Social Skills and Peer support is shown in Table 20. The data shows that teachers frequently enjoy interacting with their peers at work. This enjoyment can play a significant role in building resilience, as a positive and friendly workplace environment helps buffer against job-related stress and enhances overall well-being. Teachers report that they often can form new friendships in the workplace, as indicated by a mean score of 3.57. This skill in making new connections supports social resilience, as having multiple supportive relationships at work can provide a network of emotional and practical assistance. With a mean score of 3.49, this indicates that teachers feel relatively comfortable meeting new people. Teachers who are adept at engaging with new colleagues are more likely to foster relationships that provide support in times of stress. Teachers also find it easy to laugh with their peers, which points to positive, light-hearted interactions. Humor is often linked to reduced stress levels and an increase in overall well-being. In addition, teachers feel comfortable discussing personal issues with their peers. This openness is a key aspect of emotional resilience, as having the opportunity to talk about personal challenges can help alleviate stress and promote mental health. Moreover, teachers perceive the bonds with their peers as relatively strong. Strong peer relationships provide emotional support, validation, and practical help, which are crucial for coping with the challenges of the teaching profession. Teachers generally feel they receive support from their peers. Peer support can manifest in various forms, such as emotional encouragement, sharing teaching strategies, and providing help during difficult times.

The total mean of 3.54 indicates that, overall, teachers are highly resilient in terms of peer support and social skills in the workplace. The consistent perception of social connection, support, and enjoyment in the workplace contributes to greater resilience among teachers. The ability to connect with colleagues, form new friendships, share personal issues, and laugh together fosters a supportive and emotionally healthy environment.

The consistently high mean scores across all items indicate that teachers have well-developed social skills and strong peer support systems, which contribute significantly to their high resilience level. These interpersonal connections not only foster a positive work environment but also serve as buffers against stress, isolation, and burnout. The ability to engage in open communication, share personal experiences, and

rely on colleagues for emotional and professional support is a key factor in sustaining teachers' mental well-being and job satisfaction.

The findings also suggest that teachers operate in a collegial and socially nurturing environment, which enhances their overall capacity to cope with challenges. These social ties can encourage collaboration, reduce feelings of professional isolation, and contribute to a sense of belonging within the school community.

In conclusion, the high level of social resilience among teachers underscores the importance of maintaining and promoting a supportive peer culture in schools. Programs that encourage team building, peer mentoring, and open communication are vital to further strengthening this already solid foundation of resilience. Bray-Clark et al., (2017), explored the relationship between peer support, social skills, and teacher resilience, specifically looking at how these factors help mitigate burnout and foster emotional well-being among teachers. The study focused on the role of peer networks and the way social interactions can enhance a teacher's ability to cope with work stressors.

d. Spiritual Influences

Table 21
Resilience of Teachers in Terms of Spiritual Influences

Spiritual Influences	Mean	Analysis of Interpretation
1. Faith or God can help me overcome challenges	3.76	High
2. I believe things happen for a reason	3.85	High
3. I have to act on a hunch	3.24	Low
Total Mean	3.62	High

Table 21 shows the resilience level of teachers in terms of spiritual influences. Teachers believed that faith or God can help them overcome challenges. They also believed that things happen for a reason. These statements have weighted means of 3.76 and 3.85, respectively suggesting a high resilience level.

Teachers sometimes must act on a hunch with a mean of 3.24 inferring a low resilience in terms of spiritual influences. This means that teachers act based on their intuition and instinct during their teaching practice. They tend to trust their gut feeling at times to understand learning styles of pupils or gain control on classroom setting. The findings reveal that teachers heavily draw on spiritual beliefs to remain resilient, particularly through faith in a higher power and the conviction that life's events have meaning. These beliefs likely help them cope with professional and personal stress, providing emotional grounding, purpose, and motivation.

The high score on belief in purpose and divine help suggests that many teachers find comfort and strength in spirituality, using it as a lens to understand and endure

challenges. This is consistent with research showing that spiritual beliefs often serve as a source of inner peace and psychological resilience during times of uncertainty or stress.

On the other hand, the lower score on acting on a hunch implies that while teachers value spirituality, they may not equate it with impulsive or intuitive decision-making. Instead, their spiritual beliefs appear to be more reflective and guiding, rather than spontaneous. Teachers demonstrate a high level of resilience supported by spiritual influences, particularly through faith and meaning making. This dimension of resilience highlights the importance of respecting and supporting diverse spiritual beliefs within the educational environment, as they play a crucial role in helping teachers manage challenges with hope, optimism, and purpose.

Tantamount to this finding, Simmonds and Harris (2018) stated that the role of spiritual beliefs and intuition in shaping the resilience of educators, with a particular focus on how acting on a hunch helps teachers navigate difficult classroom situations. The study found that spirituality is a key element in fostering resilience, and teachers often rely on spiritual guidance when making decisions, especially when they feel uncertain or challenged.

5. Is there a significant difference in the teacher’s level of resilience when grouped according to profile of resilience?

a. Family Cohesion

Table 22
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion When Grouped according to their Profile

Teacher’s Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.2153	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.2431	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0500	P=0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Monthly Income	0.1310	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Workload	0.1434	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.0566	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 22 presents the results of the test of significant difference in teachers’ level of resilience in terms of family cohesion when grouped according to their profile. The

findings show that the F-probability values are greater than 0.05 for sex, age, monthly income, workload, and number of teaching loads. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference in teachers' resilience in terms of family cohesion across these variables. This means that teachers generally demonstrate similar levels of family cohesion regardless of their sex, age, income, workload, and teaching load. However, civil status emerged as a significant factor, as its F-probability value is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected for civil status, showing that single and widowed teachers have better family cohesion than married teachers.

These findings suggest that family cohesion, as a dimension of resilience, remains stable across most demographic and work-related factors, but varies according to civil status. This may be explained by differences in family structures, responsibilities, and the availability of emotional and social support among single, married, and widowed teachers. The results emphasize the need for school administrators and policymakers to consider family structure when designing support mechanisms that strengthen teachers' resilience. Boczkowska et al. (2024) similarly found that marital status influences family cohesion, social skills, and peer support.

b. Personal Competencies and Persistence

Table 23
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.0731	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.2236	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0295	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Monthly Income	0.0853	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Workload	0.0731	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.1461	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 23 shows the significant differences in teachers' resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence when grouped according to profile variables. The results reveal that sex, age, monthly income, workload, and number of teaching loads have F-probability values greater than 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted for

these variables. This indicates that teachers have similar levels of resilience in personal competencies and persistence regardless of these demographic and professional factors. However, civil status shows a significant difference since its F-probability value is less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Findings reveal that widowed teachers demonstrate higher personal competencies and persistence than single and married teachers. This suggests that civil status may influence resilience through life experiences, emotional support, and social responsibilities. The result emphasizes the need to consider civil status in resilience support programs, consistent with Mariano (2024), who found that married teachers also show high resilience.

c. Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 24
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher’s Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher’s Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.0550	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.1167	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0230	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Monthly Income	0.1207	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Workload	0.0306	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.1046	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 24 shows the significant differences in teachers’ resilience in terms of social skills and peer support when grouped by profile variables. Results indicate that civil status and workload have F-probability values below 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that teachers’ resilience in social skills and peer support significantly differs based on these variables. Widowed teachers and those with 7–10 workloads recorded the highest mean scores of 3.90 and 3.56, suggesting stronger peer support and social skills. Meanwhile, sex, age, monthly income, and number of teaching loads showed no significant differences, indicating similar resilience levels across these groups. The findings suggest that civil status and workload influence teachers’ social resilience due to variations in emotional support, social interaction, and work demands. These results emphasize the need for interventions that strengthen workplace support, consistent with Boczkowska et al. (2024), who found marital status affects social skills, peer support, and family cohesion.

d. Spiritual Influences

Table 25
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms Spiritual Influences When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and the following Profile	P-value of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sex	0.1360	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age	0.2153	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status	0.0901	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Monthly Income	0.0500	P=0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Workload	0.0250	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Teaching Loads	0.1138	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 25 presents the results of the test of significant difference in teachers' level of resilience in terms of spiritual influences when grouped according to their profile. The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 for monthly income and workloads. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is significant difference in the teachers' level of resilience in terms of spiritual influences when grouped according to their monthly income and workloads. Teachers with monthly income of ₱36,401-63,700 and with 7-10 workloads have better spiritual influences which means that income and workload significantly affect the resilience of teachers in terms of spiritual influences.

However, there is no significant difference in the teachers' level of resilience in terms of spiritual influences when grouped according to their sex, age, civil status, and number of teaching loads. It implies that the teachers have similar level of resilience on spiritual influences regardless of their sex, age, civil status, and number of teaching loads. The study of Paul et al. (2020) supported the result stating that workplace spirituality has an impact on workplace agility among teaching professions through psychological empowerment.

6. Is there a significant relationship between the state of well-being of teachers and their level of resilience?

a. Family Cohesion

Table 26
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the State of Well-being of Teachers and Their Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion

Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and the following State of Well-being	P-value of r	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Emotional Health	0.0048	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Intellectual Health	0.2517	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Physical Health	0.0219	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Health	0.1715	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Spiritual Health	0.0083	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 26 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' state of well-being and their level of resilience in terms of family cohesion. The findings show that the r-probability values for emotional, physical, and spiritual health are less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating a significant relationship between teachers' well-being in these three areas and their resilience in terms of family cohesion. This means that family cohesion significantly affects teachers' emotional, physical, and spiritual well-being. In contrast, the r-probability values for intellectual and social health are greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that teachers' intellectual and social well-being are not significantly influenced by their level of resilience in terms of family cohesion.

The results further suggest that teachers who have stronger emotional, physical, and spiritual well-being are more likely to experience greater family cohesion, which in turn strengthens their resilience. Emotional health may help teachers develop empathy, communication, and understanding within family relationships. Physical health may allow them to be more active, present, and engaged with family members. Spiritual health may also promote shared values, meaning, and purpose, which reinforce family bonds. On the other hand, intellectual health, which is related to cognitive functioning, and social health, which involves broader relationships beyond the family, do not appear to significantly shape resilience through family cohesion. These findings highlight the important role of emotional, physical, and spiritual well-being in building resilience among teachers through strong family support. This is supported by Ergün and Dewaele (2021), who concluded that happy and resilient teachers help create the positive emotional atmosphere necessary for students' growth and progress.

b. Personal Competencies and Persistence

Table 27
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the State of Well-being of Teachers and Their Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence

Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and the following State of Well-being	P-value of r	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Emotional Health	0.0139	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Intellectual Health	0.2042	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Physical Health	0.0502	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Social Health	0.1136	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Spiritual Health	0.0268	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 27 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' state of well-being and their level of resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence. The findings show that the probability values of r are less than 0.05 for emotional and spiritual health. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the teachers' emotional and spiritual well-being and their resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence. In other words, the level of resilience reflected in teachers' personal competence and persistence significantly affects their emotional and spiritual health. On the other hand, the probability values of r for intellectual, physical, and social health are greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that teachers' personal competencies and persistence do not significantly affect their intellectual, physical, and social health. The results further suggest that teachers with stronger emotional and spiritual well-being tend to demonstrate greater resilience through personal competence and persistence. Emotional health may help teachers regulate their emotions, cope with stress, and persevere in difficult situations, while spiritual health may provide meaning, purpose, and motivation that strengthen endurance and inner strength. In contrast, intellectual, physical, and social health, although important to overall well-being, do not appear to have a direct influence on this specific dimension of resilience in the present study. These findings are supported by Kärner et al. (2021), who reported that teachers with stronger resilience competencies tend to show lower anxiety as an emotional stress symptom and higher levels of job engagement. Thus, emotional and spiritual health are essential factors in strengthening teachers' resilience in terms of competencies and persistence at work.

c. Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 28
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the State of Well-being of Teachers and Their Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support

Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and the following State of Well-being	P-value of r	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Emotional Health	0.0061	$P < 0.05$	Reject Ho	Significant
Intellectual Health	0.1958	$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Physical Health	0.1750	$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Social Health	0.1961	$P > 0.05$	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Spiritual Health	0.0045	$P < 0.05$	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 28 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' state of well-being and their level of resilience in terms of social skills and peer support. The findings show that the r-probability values for emotional health and spiritual health are less than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating a significant relationship between teachers' emotional and spiritual well-being and their resilience in terms of social skills and peer support. This means that teachers' emotional and spiritual health are significantly influenced by their resilience level in building and sustaining social skills and peer support. In contrast, the r-probability values for intellectual, physical, and social health are greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that resilience in terms of social skills and peer support does not significantly affect teachers' intellectual, physical, and social health. The results suggest that teachers with stronger emotional and spiritual well-being are more capable of developing positive interpersonal relationships, empathy, effective communication, and supportive peer networks. Emotional health appears to strengthen social resilience by promoting better interactions with colleagues, while spiritual health may enhance a sense of connectedness, belongingness, and mutual support. On the other hand, intellectual, physical, and social health did not show a significant relationship with this resilience dimension, suggesting that these aspects may not directly shape peer bonding or social skills in this context. Overall, the findings emphasize the important role of emotional and spiritual well-being in strengthening teachers' social resilience. This is supported by Chakradhar et al. (2023), who found an inverse weak correlation between resilience, spiritual health, and perceived stress.

d. Spiritual Influences

Table 29
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the State of Well-being of Teachers and Their Level of Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences

Teacher's Level of Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and the following State of Well-being	P-value of r	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Emotional Health	0.2444	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Intellectual Health	0.2049	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Physical Health	0.2471	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Social Health	0.1263	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Spiritual Health	0.0043	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 29 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' state of well-being and their level of resilience in terms of spiritual influences. The findings show that the probability value of r for spiritual health is less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between the teachers' spiritual health and their resilience in terms of spiritual influences. In particular, the results suggest that teachers' resilience rooted in spiritual influences significantly affects their spiritual well-being. In contrast, there is no significant relationship between resilience in terms of spiritual influences and the teachers' emotional, intellectual, physical, and social well-being, since the probability values for these dimensions are greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted for these aspects, implying that spiritual resilience does not significantly affect them.

The findings further indicate that spiritual health holds a unique and distinct role in fostering resilience among teachers. Those with stronger spiritual well-being are more likely to rely on faith, beliefs, and a sense of purpose when facing challenges, which strengthens their capacity to cope and remain resilient. This suggests that spiritual influences serve as an important internal resource that supports teachers in managing difficulties and sustaining their sense of meaning in their profession. On the other hand, emotional, intellectual, physical, and social well-being do not appear to be directly associated with this particular dimension of resilience. These results are supported by Carneiro et al. (2019), who found that employees who are more religious and spiritualized tend to have greater resilience and are consequently less affected by burnout. Thus, spiritual health emerges as a key factor in strengthening teachers' resilience through spiritual influences.

Conclusions

The findings of this study clearly indicate that the well-being and resilience levels of teachers play a pivotal role in shaping their overall effectiveness, professional satisfaction, and long-term commitment to the teaching profession. Teachers experiencing high levels of stress, burnout, or emotional fatigue often exhibit reduced resilience and compromised well-being, which can negatively impact both instructional quality and student outcomes. One of the primary sources of this stress is the overwhelming workload that extends far beyond classroom instruction.

The study also reveals that while many teachers demonstrate high resilience, their overall state of well-being remains affected by multiple stressors including workload, administrative demands, and limited support systems. Importantly, the correlation between well-being and resilience underscores the need for a structured, evidence-based wellness program that not only addresses physical health but also promotes emotional, mental, and social support mechanisms.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the study, the following are recommended:

The Department of Education should design a national wellness framework that addresses the physical, mental, and social well-being of teachers and ensure that the program is inclusive, responsive to teachers' real needs and adaptable across regions. They can also designate wellness coordinators or guidance counselors in schools to facilitate wellness initiatives and accessible counseling services.

School Administrators should conduct regular assessments for teachers' well-being and integrate resilience training into professional development. They can help in technical assistance making flexible scheduling, fair workload distribution, including mental health provisions in HR and promote open communication, trust and inclusivity among school staff.

Mental Health Advocates can use the findings to strengthen partnerships with school and create accessible, teacher-centric wellness initiatives and should collaborate with school administrators to adopt the recommended wellness program attached. (refer to Chapter 6)

Guidance Designate/Counselor provide evidence-based insights and design targeted helpful programs, workshops and interventions that will address stress management, emotional regulation and resilience building.

School Health Personnel can support mental health officers in the school or area by integrating wellness programs, stress-relief activities and regular mental health check-ups for the teachers.

Teachers should prioritize self-care and mental health practices and engage in regular professional development and cultivate resilience by learning from challenges and setbacks in teaching. They can also reflect on this study on teaching practices that foster a collaborative rather than competitive atmosphere in the workplace.

Pupils should also help the teachers in engaging healthy learning environment.

External Stakeholders should support the teachers for a collaborative and conducive learning environment. They can also participate and make an open communication that promotes a supportive school community.

The Researcher should integrate findings into a multi-dimensional wellness framework and can recommend pilot implementation of the wellness program in the school.

Future researchers can consider comparative studies between public and private institutions or among schools/areas with different educational systems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles governing educational research. Prior to data collection, the researcher secured approval from the Schools Division Superintendent and Assistant Schools Division Superintendent, as well as permission from the School Principal of Ilagan East Integrated SPED Center. Participation of the respondents was sought only after these approvals were obtained. The respondents were properly informed of the purpose of the study, and their participation was voluntary. They were also assured that the information they provided would be treated with utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic and research purposes. No respondent was forced or coerced to participate in the study, and their dignity, privacy, and rights were respected throughout the research process. The researcher ensured that the data gathered were handled responsibly, stored securely, and reported in a manner that protected the identity of the participants.

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